

Mental Health Measurement Scales and Their Dimensions: A Systematic Review with Implications for Rajyoga Meditation Research

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DoI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20242178>

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Citation:

Dipendra Nath Subedi, Prof.(Dr.) Ajaya Bhattarai, Dr. Rajesh Arora (2026). Mental Health Measurement Scales and Their Dimensions: A Systematic Review with Implications for Rajyoga Meditation Research. International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Transactions, 8(5), 17–23. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20242178>

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Accepted: 15 May 2026

Available online: 16 May 2026

Abstract

Mental health is a complex and multidimensional construct that includes emotional, psychological and social wellbeing. In recent decades, increasing academic pressure, life style changes and social demands have led to a rise in stress, anxiety and depression, particularly among adolescents and students. Accurate assessment of mental health is essential for both clinical and educational research, as well as for evaluating intervention- based approaches such as meditation and yoga.

The present systematic review examines widely used mental health measurement scales, focusing on their conceptual dimensions, psychometric properties and applicability in research settings. Major instruments reviewed include the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS), General Health Questionnaire (GHQ), Depression Anxiety Stress Scale (DASS), Mental Health Inventory (MHI), Ryff's Psychological Well-Being Scale (PWB) and Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-

being Scale (WEMWBS). The review highlights that mental health assessment requires both negative (stress, anxiety, depression) and positive (well-being, resilience, life satisfaction) dimensions.

Findings indicate that no single scale fully captures the complexity of mental health; therefore, multi-scale approaches are recommended. Furthermore, the review identifies a significant research gap in the integration of spiritual-based interventions such as Rajyoga meditation with standardized psychometric assessments. The study concludes that combining well-being and distress measures provides a more comprehensive understanding of mental health outcomes in intervention studies.

Keywords: Mental Health, Psychological Well-being, Stress, Anxiety, Depression, Scales, Rajyoga Meditation, Psychometrics.

1. Introduction

Mental health has become a global concern in contemporary society due to increasing psychological stressors in academic, occupational, and social environments. According to the World Health Organization, mental health is not merely the absence of mental illness but a state of well-being in which individuals realize their abilities, cope with normal stresses, work productively and contribute to society.

Adolescents and young adults, particularly students, are highly vulnerable to psychological distress due to academic competition, social comparison, digital exposure and family expectations. Research consistently shows rising levels of stress, anxiety and depression among school and college students worldwide.

To address these issues, psychological researchers have developed standardized tools to measure mental health. These instruments help quantify subjective psychological states and evaluate intervention effectiveness. In recent years, complementary approaches such as mindfulness and Rajyoga meditation have gained attention for improving mental health outcomes. However, their evaluation requires reliable and multidimensional assessment tools.